

Experimental section

Materials

Oseltamivir phosphate, L-tyrosine, L-isoleucine, L-serine, L-phenylalanine, and hydroxylamine hydrochloride were purchased from Sigma/Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Triethylamine (TEA) was obtained from BDH (India). Influenza Neuraminidase Inhibitor Susceptibility Assay Kit (ab283398 / abcam / USA). MTT ((3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide). MDCK cells were purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) and cultured in high-glucose Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM).

General methods

The melting points were determined using an electrical melting point apparatus (Electro-thermal 9300, USA). Infrared spectra were recorded on a (KBr disk) using an FT-IR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 8400). ¹H-NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker 500 MHz spectrophotometer and ¹³C-NMR spectra (Avance III, 75.65 MHz spectrophotometer) were recorded using dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO-d₆) as the solvent. Chemical shifts were recorded in parts per million (ppm). Tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as an internal reference. *In vitro* cytotoxicity assay (using the MTT colorimetric assay) and neuraminidase inhibitor susceptibility tests were conducted using the Influenza Neuraminidase Inhibitor Susceptibility Assay Kit (**ab283398**) to evaluate the activities of the investigated compounds.

Chemical Syntheses

Oseltamivir carboxamides with amino acids

Oseltamivir-Phenylalanine (2-({4-(acetylamino)-5-amino-3-(pentane-2-aryloxy)cyclohex-1-en-1-yl} carbonyl} amino)-3-phenylpropanoic acid) was synthesized using oseltamivir phosphate (0.01 mole, 4.08 g) and L-phenylalanine (0.01 mole, 1.65 g), as previously described.

Oseltamivir-Isoleucine (2-(4-acetamido-5-amino-3-(pentan-3-yl) oxy) cyclohex-1-ene-1-carboxamido)-3-methylpentanoic acid was synthesized using oseltamivir phosphate (0.01 mole, 4.08 g) and L-Isoleucine (0.01 mole, 1.17 g), as previously described.

Oseltamivir-Serine (2-([4-(acetylamino)-5-amino-3-(pentane-2-aryloxy) cyclohex-1-en-1-yl] carbonyl) amino)-3-propanoic acid was synthesized using oseltamivir phosphate (0.01 mole, 4.08 g) and L-Serine (0.01 mole, 1.05 g), as previously described.

Oseltamivir-Tyrosine (2-([4-(acetylamino)-5-amino-3-(pentan-2-yloxy) cyclohex-1-en-1-yl] carbonyl) amino)-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl) propanoic acid was synthesized using Oseltamivir phosphate (0.01 mole, 4.08 g) and L-Tyrosine (0.01 mole, 1.81 g), as previously described.

Oseltamivir carboxamide hydroxamates

Oseltamivir-phenylalanine hydroxamate

Oseltamivir-Phenylalanine (1mM, 0.431g) and zinc dust (0.5 g) in dioxane (30mL) containing TEA (1mM, 1.2 mL) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1mM, 0.069 g) were treated as previously described to obtain Os-Phe-hydroxamate.

Oseltamivir-Isoleucine hydroxamate

Oseltamivir-Isoleucine (1mM, 0.383g) and zinc dust (0.5g) in dioxane (30mL) containing TEA (1mM, 1.2 mL) hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1mM, 0.069 g) and treated as previously described to afford Os-Ile-hydroxamate.

Oseltamivir-Serine hydroxamate

Oseltamivir-Serine (1mM, 0.385g) and zinc dust (0.5 g) in dioxane (30mL) containing TEA (1mM, 1.2 mL) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1mM, 0.069 g) were continuously stirred and treated as previously described to afford Os-Ser-hydroxamate.

Oseltamivir-Tyrosine hydroxamate

Oseltamivir-Tyrosine (1mM, 0.447g) and zinc dust (0.5 g) in dioxane (30mL) containing TEA (1mM, 1.2 mL) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1mM, 0.069 g) mixture were treated as previously described to afford Os-Tyr-hydroxamate.

In vitro assay for cytotoxic activity

The cytotoxicity assay was performed using the MTT colorimetric assay and the effects of the synthesized compounds were evaluated in the Madin-Darby Canine Kidney (MDCK), type (NBL-2) - CCL-34 cells.

Cell culture

MDCK cells was purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC) and cultured in high-glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM). Media were supplemented with heated fetal bovine serum (10%), L-glutamine (1%, 2mM) and penicillin (100IU/mL)/ streptomycin (100 µg/ml) from (Euro Clone). The cell growth profile was seeded in a 96-well plate at a density of 6×10^4 cells/well and cell viability was determined by trypan blue exclusion using a haemocytometer.

Assay of Cytotoxicity

MDCK Cells were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and detached with 0.025% trypsin-EDTA (Euro Clone) and media was added to a volume of 10 ml. The cell suspension was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min and the pellets were re-suspended in 10 ml medium to make a single cell suspension. Cell viability was determined by trypan blue exclusion, which exceeded 90% as counted by a haemocytometer. The cells suspension was diluted afterwards to obtain the optimal seeding density, and 100 µl aliquot was placed in a 96-well plate. The cells were cultured at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂, and incubated for 24 h and then treated with different concentrations of each compound starting from 10mM (dissolved in DMSO) in a serial dilution manner (10, 5, 2.5, 1.25, 0.62, 0.31, 0.15 and 0.078 mM) and further incubated for 72h to determine the IC₅₀ values.

Cell growth was analyzed using the MTT colorimetric assay at the end of the exposure time.

The assessment of cell viability using the MTT colorimetric assay

The newly synthesized compounds were tested for the cell viability using an MTT colorimetric assay. MTT stock solution (15µl, 5 mg/ml) in sterile PBS (pH 7.4) was incubated for 72 h and placed in each well. The cells were then added to each well and

incubated for a further 3 h in the presence of a solubilizing stop solution (100 μ L) to solubilize the dark violet formazan crystals. The optical density was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader. The results are expressed as the percentage of cell viability compared with the control, corresponding to untreated cells.

Determination of the half-maximal inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀ values)

The IC₅₀ values for the investigated compounds were determined by constructing a dose-response curve. In the MTT assay, IC₅₀ values denote the concentrations of compounds necessary to achieve a 50% reduction in cell viability. Based on the acquired data, the IC₅₀ values were determined after a 72 h of exposure of the cells to the tested compounds. To ascertain the IC₅₀ values, a concentration range consisting of the following concentrations (10-0.078 μ M) was used.

Influenza Neuraminidase inhibition ELISA assay

Determination of the appropriate dilution factor for H1N1 viral strain

4-Methylumbeliferone (4-MU) was used as a standard and by diluting the stock solution (5 mM, 10 μ L) to Neuraminidase assay buffer (990 μ L) to obtain the working solution (50 μ M). Using the compounds at concentrations (0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6 and 2.0 nM /well) and the 4-MU standard was prepared by adding 0, 2, 4, 8, 16, 24, 32 and 40 μ L of the 50 μ M solution into a series of wells, and the volume was adjusted for each well to 100 μ L with neuraminidase assay buffer. Neuraminidase Stop Solution (100 μ L) was added to each well (final volume of 200 μ L/well) mixed thoroughly. The fluorescence of solution in the wells was measured at Ex/Em = 368/460 nm, the 0 nM /well (RFU) reading was subtracted from all of the standard readings, and the slope of the 4-MU standard curve was constructed. A series of 12 reaction wells from the H1N1 viral strain (one row of a 96-blank well plate) was prepared by adding neuraminidase assay buffer (50 μ L) to each well in columns 1-12. 50 microliters of undiluted H1N1 viral isolate were added to column 1 and mixed thoroughly. A series of 2-fold serial dilutions were performed across the row of wells by transferring 50 μ L from column 1 to column 2 and mixing the contents, until column 11 was reached. Fifty microliters from column 11 were discarded, leaving column 12 to serve as a background control well (no virus) to correct for non-enzymatic substrate hydrolysis. The volume of each well was 50 μ L. The (96-dark well plate) was incubated at 37°C for 10 min to equilibrate the contents of the wells to the reaction temperature. During

incubation, a concentrated neuraminidase substrate working solution (2X) was prepared by diluting the reconstituted neuraminidase substrate stock solution (100X) with neuraminidase assay buffer at a 1:50 ratio. Neuraminidase substrate solution (50 μ l, 2X) was added to each reaction well, and the volume was brought to 100 μ L/well. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 60 min in the dark. The reaction was terminated by addition of Neuraminidase Stop Solution (100 μ L) to each well. The contents were thoroughly mixed and the fluorescence of the solutions was measured at Ex/Em= 368/460 nm.

Determination of the dilution factor corresponds to the RFU value

The fluorescence (F) was quantified by subtracting the mean fluorescence intensity of the solution containing no virus background control wells (RFU blank) from the fluorescence intensity of each sample well (RFU sample): $F = \text{RFU sample} - \text{RFU blank}$.

For the H1N1 viral strain, background-subtracted F values were plotted against the sample dilution factor. This value was used as the viral dilution factor in the inhibitor susceptibility assay.

Neuraminidase Inhibitor Susceptibility Assay

A set protocol was used to evaluate NA susceptibility, as follows; each tested compound was dissolved in DMSO solvent at final concentrations of less than (2%, v/v) to produce a master stock solution (10 mM). Working solution (1 mM) was prepared by diluting the master stock with neuraminidase assay buffer at a 1:10 ratio. The working solutions (4X) were prepared in a range of concentrations by diluting the working solution in neuraminidase assay buffer (to generate a multi-point dose-response curve) and to determine IC₅₀ values for each compound. A series of working solutions (ten, 4X) were prepared in neuraminidase assay buffer (0.04, 0.2, 0.4, 2, 4, 20, 40, 400, 4000, and 40000 nM, corresponding to a final concentration range of 1 μ M to 10 μ M). H1N1 viral strain to be tested for susceptibility, a series of reaction wells were prepared containing 25 μ L of each 4X test concentration (working solution) as well as the corresponding no-inhibitor control (containing neuraminidase assay buffer, 25 μ L) and background control wells (containing 50 μ L neuraminidase assay buffer). The H1N1 viral isolate stock solution was diluted with neuraminidase assay buffer according to the optimal dilution factor determined

in the neuraminidase activity viral titration assay. The plate was incubated at 37°C for 30 min to allow the inhibitors to interact with the viral enzymes. During the incubation, a concentrated neuraminidase substrate working solution (2X) was prepared by diluting the reconstituted neuraminidase substrate stock solution (100X) with Neuraminidase assay buffer at a 1:50 ratio. A neuraminidase substrate solution (50 µL, 2X) was prepared for each well.

Neuraminidase Reaction

The reaction was started by adding a neuraminidase substrate working solution (50 µL, 2X) to each reaction well, bringing the volume to 100 µl/well. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 60 min in the dark. The reaction was terminated by adding a neuraminidase stop solution (100 µL) to each well. The contents were mixed thoroughly and the fluorescence of all wells was measured at Ex/Em = 368/460 nm. For each reaction well, including no inhibitor/vehicle controls, the fluorescence intensity of the background control well (RFU blank) was subtracted to determine the background-corrected fluorescence (denoted by F). For each NI test concentration (FNI) in the dose-response curve, the percent inhibition (or remaining activity) relative to the vehicle control (FVC) was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Relative Inhibition} = FVC - FNI / FVC \times 100$$

$$\text{Relative Activity (\%)} = FNI / FVC \times 100$$

The relative activity (or percent inhibition) at each NI concentration was plotted and the IC₅₀ values were calculated by non-linear logistic curve fitting.